

STUDIES ON MAHUA STEROL FROM *BASSIA LATIFOLIA*

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Bassia latifolia or *Madhuka indica*, known in Hindi as 'Mahua' and in Sanskrit as 'Atavimadhuka' is one of the abundantly growing plants in India. The fruit of the plant is highly medicinal and the oil therefrom is much used by the hill tribes in the treatment of scurvy.

The fat obtained from the kernels of the plant is known as 'Mahua butter' in Hindusthani and 'Illipe butter' in English. From a survey of literature, it is concluded that the earlier workers could throw no light on the chemical constitution of the unsaponifiable matter of Mahua oil. This led the authors to investigate the nature of the unsaponifiables.

The present investigation reveals that Mahua oil contains 2.53% of unsaponifiable matter and a gummy semisolid mass, which makes up the rest. From this unsaponifiable matter, two sterols, m.p. 117° and 122° respectively, have been isolated by chromatographic method. The higher melting sterol on fractional crystallisation, according to the technique adopted by Anderson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2976, 2987), showed no further alteration in specific rotation. Its molecular formula is found to be $C_{28}H_{48}O$. It appears to be isomeric with β - and γ -sitosterols (Windaus, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1254, 1689; Dirscel, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1939, 257, 239) but possesses a higher specific rotation $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 57^\circ.9$ (chloroform) and lower m.p. 122° than any of the isomeric sterols. It has been found to contain one double bond, and one hydroxyl group. The characteristics of the sterol have further been confirmed by the formation of a digitonide, m.p. 220° (decomp.) and liberation of the original sterol, showing the presence of a 3- β -hydroxyl group in the molecule.

Isolation of Sterol.—The oil (2 kg.) (obtained from the seeds in 41% yield) was saponified with 20% NaOH solution and extracted with petroleum ether. The extract after washing with water and drying over calcium chloride was distilled, when 43.8 g of the unsaponifiable matter was obtained. This product was dissolved in methyl alcohol and kept in a frigidaire overnight, when the precipitate of the sterol (20.3%) and a large amount of a brown gummy residue (79.7%) were obtained. The precipitate after dissolution in petroleum ether and keeping in a frigidiare, melted at 112-118°. This crude product was separated into two sterols: (1) m.p. 117°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 43^\circ.5$ ($CHCl_3$) and (2) m.p. 120-22°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 57^\circ.5$ ($CHCl_3$).

Fractionation of Mahua Sterol.—The product (7.15 g.), obtained above, was fractionated by repeated crystallisations from ether-alcohol mixture and finally crystallised from absolute alcohol, when colorless plates, m.p. 117°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 43^\circ.7$, were obtained. This product being in a minute quantity and impure, could not be used for further investigation.

Mahua sterol crystallises in flakes, m.p. 122° . It is soluble in benzene, chloroform and petroleum ether but sparingly soluble in cold methyl or ethyl alcohol. It gives positive Salkowski's reaction and in the Liebermann-Burchard reaction it assumes a pink colour, which quickly changes to green. In the Steinle-Khlenberg reaction, a purple coloration is observed, which on exposure to light turns cobalt blue. (Found: C, 84.23; H, 11.98. M. W., 430. $C_{29}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.05; H, 12.08%).

Monoacetyl derivative of the Mahua sterol was prepared as usual and crystallised from absolute alcohol in needles, m.p. $113-14^{\circ}$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 52.9^{\circ}$, yield 80.3%. (Found: C, 81.46; H, 11.38. $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 81.58; H, 11.4%).

Monobenzoyl derivative of the product was obtained as usual and was crystallised from ethyl acetate in clusters, m.p. 130° , $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 26^{\circ}.5$ ($CHCl_3$). (Found: C, 83.52; H, 10.38. $C_{36}H_{54}O_2$ requires C, 83.4; H, 10.42%).

Digitonide derivative was prepared by heating under reflux a mixture of sterol (0.5 g.) and digitonin (0.5 g.), dissolved in alcohol for 2 hours and keeping the contents in a frigidaire overnight. The flocculent precipitate was washed with alcohol and ether and dried. The compound melted at 220° . (Found: C, 61.86; H, 8.58. $C_{29}H_{50}O.C_{55}H_{90}O_{21}$ requires C, 61.91; H, 8.6%).

Mahua sterol acetate dibromide.—The sterol acetate was brominated by the method of Windaus and Hauth (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4378). The sterol acetate dibromide formed a slightly yellowish amorphous powder, m.p. 108° . (Found: Br, 25.88. $C_{31}H_{52}O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 25.97%).

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